

1 **Revisiting a recent study on canine colibacillosis: insights for One Health and veterinary**
2 **Practice**

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26 **Abstract**

27 Within a One Health framework, diagnostic inaccuracies in companion animals can
28 propagate inappropriate antimicrobial use, distort zoonotic risk perception, and undermine public
29 health surveillance. This correspondence critically evaluates the methodology and conclusions of
30 Jaafar et al. (2025), titled “*Immunity, antioxidant activity, and antibiotic susceptibility of*
31 *clinically and phylogenetically confirmed colibacillosis in dogs with gastrointestinal disease*”,
32 published in the *Open Veterinary Journal*. Five major methodological limitations compromise
33 the study's validity: (1) reliance on 16S rRNA sequencing that cannot distinguish pathogenic
34 from commensal *E. coli*; (2) internal contradictions in Sorbitol MacConkey (SMAC) results
35 without consideration of O157:H7 implications; (3) unsupported claims of interspecies and
36 zoonotic transmission; (4) lack of a healthy control group, undermining immune and antioxidant
37 analyses; (5) inappropriate comparison with literature using incompatible methods. These
38 oversights carry implications beyond veterinary practice, including risks to antimicrobial
39 stewardship, diagnostic accuracy, and One Health surveillance. Strengthening study design and
40 methodological rigor is essential to protect animal health, public health, and environmental
41 safety.

42 **Key words:** Antibiotic susceptibility; Antioxidant activity; Canine colibacillosis; *Escherichia*
43 *coli*; Immunity; Iraq; One Health.

44 **Main text**

45 I read with interest, but with great concern, the recent article published in *Open*
46 *Veterinary Journal* titled “Immunity, antioxidant activity, and antibiotic susceptibility of
47 clinically and phylogenetically confirmed colibacillosis in dogs with gastrointestinal disease”
48 (Jaafar *et al.*, 2025). Although the study addresses an important topic, several critical scientific

49 and methodological weaknesses undermine the validity of its findings and their broader clinical
50 and epidemiological implications.

51 In this critique, I identify five major concerns and address each in light of existing
52 literature on canine colibacillosis, highlighting what was done incorrectly, the potential negative
53 impact on veterinary and public health practice, and the more robust methodological approaches
54 that should have been adopted.

55 **1. Concern 1 — “*Clinically confirmed colibacillosis*” is unjustified**

56 **1.1. What is wrong?**

57 The authors based their diagnosis of “*clinically confirmed colibacillosis*” solely on
58 culture and 16S rRNA PCR/sequencing. This methodology identifies bacteria at the species (or
59 sometimes genus) level but cannot distinguish pathogenic from commensal *E. coli*.

60 **1.2. What are the negative impacts?**

61 Since *E. coli* can be isolated from healthy canine intestines, relying solely on culture and
62 16S risks misclassifying commensal strains as pathogens. If the isolates were in fact commensal
63 strains rather than true pathogenic *E. coli*, labeling them as “*clinically confirmed colibacillosis*”
64 could have serious clinical and epidemiological consequences as outlined below.

65 **1.2.1. Risk of inappropriate antimicrobial use**

66 Although studying antimicrobial resistance in commensal *E. coli* is valuable for
67 surveillance, presenting such data within an unjustified disease context can create the false
68 impression that the reported susceptibility profile serves as an empirical treatment guide.

69 Misclassification of commensal strains as pathogens may mislead veterinarians, causing
70 inappropriate antimicrobial use. This increases antimicrobial resistance, which can spill over to
71 humans and the environment.

72 **1.2.2. Misguide researchers and diagnostic laboratories**

73 Junior researchers, who often consult published literature to learn methodology, and low-
74 resource diagnostic laboratories, which may lack access to confirmatory tests, could adopt the
75 same flawed diagnostic approaches reported in the study. This propagation of inadequate
76 methodology can lead to inaccurate disease attribution and undermine both antimicrobial
77 stewardship and One-Health surveillance efforts.

78 **1.3. What appropriate methodology should have been used?**

79 To claim *E. coli* is the causative agent of enteritis (i.e., colibacillosis), the authors were
80 supposed to do the following steps:

81 **1.3.1. Determine the pathogenic potential of the isolated *E. coli***

82 The initial step is to determine whether the isolated *E. coli* strains possess the pathogenic
83 potential to cause enteritis or merely represent commensal flora. This can be achieved by
84 screening for key virulence genes that define diarrhegenic *E. coli* (DEC) pathotypes. Ideally, at
85 least three to five well-isolated colonies from the same sample should be tested, since *E. coli*
86 may exist as a mixed population within a single host (Feitosa *et al.*, 2024; Sancak *et al.*, 2004).

87 In dogs, the following DEC pathotypes, alongside their defining virulence genes, have
88 been documented: Enteropathogenic *E. coli* (EPEC), characterized by the presence of *eae* but
89 absence of *stx*; both typical (tEPEC, carrying *bfpA*) and atypical (aEPEC, lacking *bfpA*) variants
90 have been detected (Coura *et al.*, 2014; Feitosa *et al.*, 2024; Puño-Sarmiento *et al.*, 2013;
91 Rodrigues *et al.*, 2004). Shiga toxin-producing *E. coli* (STEC) are defined by *stx1* and/or *stx2*,
92 while enterohemorrhagic *E. coli* (EHEC), a clinically important subset of STEC, harbor both *stx*
93 and *eae* (Coura *et al.*, 2014; Sancak *et al.*, 2004; Staats *et al.*, 2003; Vračar *et al.*, 2023).
94 Additional pathotypes include enteroaggregative *E. coli* (EAEC, *aggR*) (Puño-Sarmiento *et al.*,

95 2013), enterotoxigenic *E. coli* (ETEC, *elt* and/or *est*) (Staats *et al.*, 2003), and necrotoxicogenic *E.*
96 *coli* (NTEC, *cnf*) (Coura *et al.*, 2014).

97 While most available studies show that aEPEC is the dominant pathotype in dogs (Coura
98 *et al.*, 2014; Feitosa *et al.*, 2024; Puño-Sarmiento *et al.*, 2013; Sancak *et al.*, 2004), screening for
99 all major virulence genes using multiplex PCR remains ideal for individual diagnostics.

100 Additionally, multiplex PCR provides valuable epidemiological data to establish baseline
101 prevalence and relative frequencies of DEC pathotypes in dog populations, which remain limited
102 globally and regionally. Such information can guide future targeted screening strategies.

103 **1.3.2. Comparison with a control healthy group for frequency or expression of virulence** 104 **genes**

105 A critical methodological gap in the study is that the authors did not include a healthy
106 control group. From an epidemiological perspective, to establish a pathogenic role of *E. coli* in
107 canine enteritis, a crucial next step would have been to compare the frequency of pathotypes in
108 diarrheic versus clinically healthy dogs. This step is essential because most previous
109 epidemiological studies have failed to demonstrate a consistent association between the presence
110 of *E. coli* pathotypes and diarrhea in dogs (Bentancor *et al.*, 2007; Coura *et al.*, 2014; de Almeida
111 *et al.*, 2012; Nakazato *et al.*, 2004; Staats *et al.*, 2003; Vračar *et al.*, 2023), while only a few have
112 reported a positive association (Hasan *et al.*, 2016; Puño-Sarmiento *et al.*, 2013). Repeating and
113 expanding such comparisons is necessary to clarify this long-standing uncertainty.

114 Moreover, even if a simple presence/absence comparison were to show no significant
115 association, the analysis should be extended beyond gene detection to include gene expression
116 levels (e.g., mRNA detection by qRT-PCR) or toxin production (e.g., ELISA for STEC or ETEC)
117 in both healthy and diarrheic dogs. This would provide a more accurate assessment of the role of

118 actively expressed virulence factors in disease, offering stronger epidemiological and biological
119 evidence of true pathogenic involvement.

120 To further illustrate this concept, I re-analyzed raw data from a previously published
121 study (Staats *et al.*, 2003) by redefining STEC pathotype as isolates harboring stx1 and/or stx2
122 genes. This re-analysis revealed a non-significant association between STEC pathotype presence
123 and diarrhea. Notably, in the original study, the authors found a significant association between
124 Shiga toxin detection by ELISA and diarrhea (Table 1).

125 This discrepancy highlights that the mere presence of virulence genes does not
126 necessarily equate to their expression or pathogenic effect, emphasizing the added
127 epidemiological value of incorporating functional assays in comparisons.

128 **1.3.3. Comprehensive diagnostic approach for other enteric pathogens**

129 While the authors claim “clinically confirmed colibacillosis,” the study did not assess the
130 presence of other enteric pathogens that could contribute to diarrhea. A more comprehensive
131 diagnostic approach would include screening for viral agents (canine parvovirus, enteric
132 coronavirus, distemper, rotavirus), parasitic agents (roundworms, hookworms, *Giardia*, *Isospora*,
133 *Cryptosporidium*), and bacterial pathogens (*Clostridium perfringens*, *Campylobacter*, *Shigella*,
134 *Salmonella*).

135 This approach is essential for contextualizing the role of DEC, whether as primary
136 pathogens or secondary invaders, and for guiding informed clinical decision-making. Previous
137 retrospective and prospective studies have successfully employed multi-pathogen assessments to
138 elucidate the pathogenic significance of *E. coli* in canine enteritis (Rodrigues *et al.*, 2004;
139 Kjaergaard *et al.*, 2016; Turk *et al.*, 1998).

140 **2. Concern 2 — The internal contradiction and missed opportunity to contextualize**
141 **findings within national literature**

142 **2.1. What is wrong?**

143 The authors reported that all *E. coli* isolates were colorless on Sorbitol MacConkey agar
144 (SMA), yet in the biochemical tests, they described a positive sorbitol reaction. This
145 inconsistency casts doubt on the reliability of the methods and the accuracy of the results. The
146 study does not address this discrepancy. furthermore, it does not acknowledge that colorless
147 colonies on SMA may indicate the O157:H7 serotype, which is significant for zoonotic
148 transmission.

149 **2.2. What are the negative impacts?**

150 The O157:H7 serotype is strongly associated with severe human illnesses, including
151 hemorrhagic colitis and hemolytic uremic syndrome (Bentancor *et al.*, 2007). Previous studies
152 that performed serotyping of *E. coli* in dogs have reported a 0% detection rate in Argentina
153 (Bentancor *et al.*, 2007), the UK (Sancak *et al.*, 2004), and the U.S. (Jay-Russell *et al.*, 2014;
154 Staats *et al.*, 2003), and a very low prevalence (0.16%) in Japan (Kataoka *et al.*, 2010).
155 Experimental infections in dogs with this serotype have typically resulted in either no clinical
156 signs or transient, self-limiting diarrhea (Kusunoki *et al.*, 2004; Wang *et al.*, 2006). In contrast, a
157 previous study conducted in Iraq has documented an exceptionally high prevalence of O157:H7
158 (68% in diarrheic dogs, 8% in healthy controls) with a significant association with diarrhea
159 (Hasan *et al.*, 2016).

160 The authors' failure to address the potential presence of O157:H7 in their isolates and to
161 engage with prior national research reporting such high prevalence represents a major missed
162 opportunity. Discussing this unique regional epidemiology could have provided crucial insight

163 into the health impact of this serotype in dogs and its potential role as a zoonotic reservoir with
164 serious public health implications.

165 **2.3. What appropriate methodology should have been used?**

166 Even if colorless colonies on SMA are suggestive of O157:H7 on their own (Jay-Russell
167 *et al.*, 2014), such a finding should have immediately raised suspicion and prompted further
168 characterization. Specific serotyping based on somatic (O) and flagellar (H) antigens, for
169 example, using a latex agglutination test, should have been performed.

170 Importantly, detection of O157:H7 alone does not necessarily confirm pathogenicity, as
171 the previous Iraqi study found that 4 out of 18 O157:H7 isolates lacked EPEC- or EHEC-
172 associated virulence genes (Hasan *et al.*, 2016). Therefore, following serotyping, a multiplex
173 PCR targeting multiple virulence genes should have been conducted to determine the pathogenic
174 potential of the isolates. Moreover, integrate findings into regional zoonotic risk assessment
175 frameworks to inform One Health monitoring.

176 **3. Concern 3 — Questionable claims of dog–chicken *E. coli* strain identity and zoonotic** 177 **transmission**

178 **3.1. What is wrong?**

179 In their discussion, the authors reported high nucleotide identity between their canine *E.*
180 *coli* strains and a strain previously isolated from a chicken in Iraq, claiming this supports animal-
181 to-animal and animal-to-human transmission. This conclusion is scientifically unsound because
182 they relied on 16S rRNA gene sequencing, a highly conserved marker. Due to its limited
183 resolution, 16S rRNA cannot reliably distinguish strains or confirm transmission pathways,
184 making any inference about interspecies or zoonotic spread highly questionable.

185 **3.2. What are the negative impacts?**

186 Overstating the significance of sequence similarity as evidence of transmission can
187 mislead public health authorities, potentially diverting surveillance efforts and resources toward
188 a perceived threat that may not exist. It may also create unnecessary concern among pet owners,
189 leading to unwarranted changes in animal handling or the demand for prophylactic or
190 unnecessary antibiotic treatments, which could contribute to antimicrobial resistance and further
191 public health challenges.

192 3.3. What appropriate methodology should have been used?

193 To robustly support claims of animal-to-animal or zoonotic transmission, the authors
194 should have demonstrated that the isolates are clonal. This requires establishing high-resolution
195 similarity at the serological, phenotypic, and genetic levels. Serological typing of O and H
196 antigens provides the initial antigenic profile, enabling comparison of shared serotypes between
197 hosts. Phenotypic assays, such as adherence pattern characterization on cultured cells, can further
198 confirm functional similarity in host–pathogen interactions. In parallel, detailed virulence gene
199 profiling and subtyping, for example, in the case of EPEC, targeting *eae*, *tir*, and *espA* genes and
200 their subtypes (α , β , γ , etc.), is critical for determining whether the isolates share similar
201 pathogenic signatures.

202 Finally, high-resolution genetic analyses using techniques such as Enterobacterial
203 Repetitive Intergenic Consensus–Polymerase Chain Reaction, Random Amplified Polymorphic
204 DNA analysis, Multilocus Sequence Typing, Pulsed-Field Gel Electrophoresis, or whole genome
205 sequencing are necessary to demonstrate overall genomic similarity and clonality, providing
206 evidence of shared lineages beyond virulence genes alone. Only through this comprehensive,
207 multi-tiered approach could one reliably infer potential transmission pathways. Please refer to

208 relevant studies for further methodological details and application (Arais *et al.*, 2018; Rodrigues
209 *et al.*, 2004).

210 **4. Concern 4 — When controls are missing: doubts on immune marker reliability**

211 **What is wrong?**

212 The study compared two groups (*E. coli*-positive versus *E. coli*-negative), both
213 exhibiting gastrointestinal signs. Consequently, any observed differences cannot be confidently
214 attributed to *E. coli* infection, as other enteric pathogens or the overall disease state may have
215 contributed to these changes.

216 **What are the negative impacts?**

217 This design, combined with the lack of confirmation of the pathogenic potential of the
218 isolated strains, casts doubt on the reliability of the reported immune marker and antioxidant
219 results. Veterinarians may incorrectly assume that changes in immune markers or antioxidant
220 status are specific to *E. coli* infection, potentially influencing diagnostic decisions, including
221 unnecessary interventions or inappropriate use of immunomodulators or antioxidants.

222 **What appropriate methodology should have been used?**

223 Confirming isolates' pathogenic potential, screening for co-infections, and using a
224 healthy control group would allow reliable attribution of immune and antioxidant changes
225 specifically to pathogenic *E. coli*.

226 **5. Concern 5 — Inappropriate comparison with existing literature regarding disease 227 prevalence**

228 **What is wrong?**

229 In their discussion, the authors compare their estimated prevalence of *E. coli* isolates with
230 results from several previously published studies. However, most of those cited studies did not

231 investigate overall *E. coli* prevalence nor assess pathogenic potential. Instead, they applied
232 targeted methodologies designed specifically to detect extended β -lactam-resistant *E. coli* strains
233 only. Because these studies capture only a limited subset of *E. coli* populations, their reported
234 prevalence values are not directly comparable with the broader prevalence measured in the Iraqi
235 study.

236 **What are the negative impacts?**

237 The inconsistency in methodological scope between the Iraqi study and previous ones renders
238 the comparisons inappropriate and undermines the interpretive value and scientific purpose of
239 the discussion. Such invalid comparisons may distort our understanding of regional
240 epidemiology, potentially leading to misinformed control strategies.

241 **What appropriate methodology should have been used?**

242 Comparisons should be made with studies using compatible detection methods and target
243 populations. When no directly comparable studies exist, the authors should clearly acknowledge
244 methodological differences and their impact on interpretability.

245 **Conclusion**

246 This correspondence highlights a One Health-oriented, clinical, and educational
247 perspective, emphasizing the risks of misdiagnosis in veterinary practice, the potential for
248 misinterpretation of zoonotic risks in public health, and the importance of adopting robust and
249 methodologically sound approaches in research.

250 **Declarations**

251 **Ethics approval and consent to participate**

252 Not applicable

253 **Consent for publication**

254 Not applicable

255 **Availability of data and materials**

256 Not applicable

257 **Competing interests**

258 The author declares that he has no competing interests.

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263 Mahmoud S. Safwat is the sole author and was responsible for the conception, analysis,
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348 **Table 1.** Association between Shiga toxins or their genes and diarrhea in dogs in a previous study

349 (Staats *et al.*, 2003).

		Health status		<i>n</i>	<i>P</i> value ^c
		Diarrheic	Healthy		
STEC pathotype genes ^a	Present	19	27	46	0.636
	Absent	41	49	90	
Shiga toxins ^b	Present	26	18	44	0.015
	Absent	34	58	92	
<i>N</i>		60	76	136	

350 ^a Results were re-analyzed from the raw data of the previous study. For this re-analysis, any dog
351 harboring stx1 and/or stx2 was considered positive for the STEC pathotype for more biologically
352 meaningful evidence, in contrast to the original study that analyzed each gene separately.

353 ^b Results were reported in the previous study using ELISA, which does not differentiate between
354 Shiga toxin 1 and 2.

355 ^c*P* value was calculated using Pearson’s chi-square test; $P < 0.05$ was considered statistically
356 significant (shown in bold). These results indicate that the mere presence of stx1 and/or stx2
357 genes is not associated with diarrhea, whereas the presence of Shiga toxins themselves is
358 associated with diarrhea, highlighting the importance of functional assays in evaluating the
359 pathogenic role of *Escherichia coli* in canine enteritis.